

Holistic Modeling Approach for Enterprise Architecture

Thesis Master of Science in Business Informatics

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Abstract

The discipline of Enterprise Architecture has evolved over the past few years to become an important tool for organizations. Digitalization and the increasingly rapid pace of market change mean that companies must be able to adapt and reposition themselves quickly. In this context, it is essential to have an overview of one's own business and IT. There are already many established frameworks, modeling languages and tools on the market that professionals are familiar with. In order to get the most out of the architecture, this thesis has developed a method and a prototype for creating a holistic enterprise architecture. All sub-architectures according to TOGAF with the well-known state-of-the-art modeling languages ArchiMate, e3-Value, BPMN 2.0 and UML should be able to be mapped and connected in the same tool. The prototype is a good basis for mapping an enterprise architecture, whether in a company or for educational purposes. However, there are a number of improvements that have already been outlined in this paper and can be considered for further development.

Keywords:

Enterprise Architecture, ArchiMate, e3-Value Method, BPMN 2.0, UML

Contents

Abbreviations	iv
List of figures	vi
List of tables	vii
1. Introduction	2
1.1. Problem Statement	2
1.2. Research Questions	3
1.3. Structure of Work	4
2. Methodology	6
2.1. Analysis	8
2.2. Design	8
2.3. Evaluation	8
2.4. Communication	9
3. Fundamentals of Enterprise Architecture Management	10
3.1. History of the Development	13
3.2. The Purpose and Impact of an Enterprise Architecture	13
3.3. Roles in Enterprise Architecture	16
3.4. Enterprise Architecture Tools	18
4. Existing Modeling Concepts	19
4.1. Enterprise Architecture Implementation Methodologies	19
4.1.1. The Open Group Architecture Framework (TOGAF)	20
4.2. State-of-the-art Modeling methods	23
4.2.1. ArchiMate	23
4.2.2. e3-Value Method	25
4.2.3. BPMN 2.0	27
4.2.4. UML	29

5. Solution Approach for Holistic Enterprise Architecture Modeling	30
5.1. Holistic Enterprise Architecture Model	30
5.1.1. ArchiMate and e3-Value	32
5.1.2. ArchiMate and BPMN 2.0	33
5.1.3. ArchiMate and UML	36
5.2. Links Between the Modeling Languages	37
5.2.1. e3-Value and BPMN 2.0	37
5.2.2. e3-Value and UML	38
5.2.3. BPMN 2.0 and UML	38
6. Prototype of a Modeling Toolkit for a Holistic Enterprise Architecture	40
6.1. ADOxx	40
6.2. Libraries	41
6.2.1. Bee-Up	42
6.2.2. TEAM	43
6.2.3. MABBM	43
6.3. Implementation of Holistic Approach	44
6.3.1. Merging of the Libraries	44
6.3.2. Model Types	47
6.3.3. Extensions Holistic EA	49
7. Evaluation	52
7.1. Scenario-based Evaluation	52
7.1.1. Introduction to the Example	53
7.1.2. Folder Structure	55
7.1.3. Enterprise Architecture	56
7.1.4. Business Architecture	58
7.1.5. Information System Architecture	61
7.1.6. Technology Architecture	62
7.1.7. Holistic EA	63
7.1.8. Conclusion of the Scenario-based Evaluation	64
7.2. Assessment of the Modeling Methodology and Prototype	65
7.2.1. SWOT Analysis	65
8. Discussion and Outlook	68
8.1. Additional Connections to the Enterprise Architecture	68
8.2. ArchiMate Full Framework	68
8.3. Extension of Loose Coupling of Elements	69
8.4. Extension with Additional Modeling Languages	69
8.5. Further Development	70
8.5.1. Automatically Store Bidirectional Function	70

8.5.2. Annotation Concept	70
8.6. Further Uses	71
References	72
Web Resourcen	74
A. Deployment of the Prototype - Library Holistic EA	76
B. Meta Model Library Holistic EA	77

Abbreviations

ADM	Architecture Development Method
ALL	ADOxx Library Language
BMC	Business Model Canvas
BPM	Business Process Management
BPMN	Business Process Model and Notation
BU	Business Unit
CMDB	Configuration Management Database
DoDAF	Department of Defense Architectural Framework
DSR	Design Science Research
EA	Enterprise Architecture
EAIM	Enterprise Architecture Implementation Methodology
EAM	Enterprise Architecture Management
EAP	Enterprise Architecture Planning
EPC	Event-Driven Process Chain
FEA	Federal Enterprise Architecture
ISO	International Organization for Standardization
KPI	Key performance indicator
MABBM	Modeling Approach for Blockchain-inspired Business Models
OMG	Object Management Group
OMiLAB	Open Model Initiative Laboratory
SeMFIS	Semantic-based Modelling Framework for Information Systems
SWOT	Strengths, Weaknesses, Opportunities and Threats
TEAM	TOGAF based Enterprise Architecture Management
TOGAF	The Open Group Architecture Framework
UML	Unified Modeling Language

List of Figures

1.	Overview of the methodology used	7
2.	Architecture pyramid	11
3.	Benefits of Enterprise Architecture Management	15
4.	TOGAF Documentation Set	20
5.	Architecture Development Cycle	21
6.	Components of modeling methods	23
7.	ArchiMate Core Framework	24
8.	ArchiMate Core Elements	25
9.	e3-Value Method	27
10.	UML 2.0 diagrams	29
11.	References to the ArchiMate Business Layer	31
12.	References to the ArchiMate Application Layer	31
13.	References to the ArchiMate Technology Layer	32
14.	Links between BPMN 2.0 and UML	39
15.	Roles and languages in the modeling hierarchy of ADOxx	41
16.	ADOxx models of the Bee-Up tool	42
17.	ADOxx models of the TEAM tool	43
18.	ArchiMate elements in Holistic EA library	45
19.	ArchiMate relations in Holistic EA library	46
20.	MABBM elements in Holistic EA library	46
21.	MABBM relations in Holistic EA library	47
22.	Example of links in a notebook	51
23.	Overview of the model types and linkages of the example	54
24.	Example: Folder structure Explorer ADOxx	55
25.	Example: Enterprise Architecture - Process Landscape	56
26.	Example: Enterprise Architecture - Application Landscape	57

27.	Example: Enterprise Architecture - Analysis Model BU Sales	58
28.	Example: Business Architecture - Overview Core Processes	59
29.	Example: Business Architecture - Process "Ticket sales counter"	59
30.	Example: Business Architecture - References	60
31.	Example: Business Architecture - e3-Value Method	60
32.	Example: Information System Architecture - Class Diagram Ticket sales counter	61
33.	Example: Information System Architecture - Links to BPMN 2.0 elements	62
34.	Example: Technology Architecture - Deployment Diagram Database for Ticket system	62
35.	Example: Holistic EA - Connected processes	63
36.	Example: Holistic EA - Connected applications	64
37.	Example: Holistic EA - Connected components	64
38.	Meta model of the Holistic EA Library	77

List of Tables

1.	Guiding principles of DSR accoring to Hevner et al.	6
2.	Dimensions of the Business Architecture	12
3.	Disadvantages of a holistic Enterprise Architecture	16
4.	Roles in enterprise architecture	17
5.	Description of the ADM cycle	22
6.	ArchiMate Layers of the Core Framework	24
7.	ArchiMate Aspects of the Core Framework	25
8.	e3-Value Method: Elements	26
9.	Extension MABBM	27
10.	BPMN 2.0 basic modeling elements	28
12.	ArchiMate and e3-Value	33
14.	ArchiMate and BPMN 2.0	35
16.	ArchiMate and UML	37
17.	Contents of the ADOxx libraries	41
18.	Model types Holistic EA prototype	48
19.	Details of the relation "RepresentedBy"	49
20.	New Interref-Attributes	50
21.	SWOT analysis	65
22.	Description of internal SWOT analysis	66
23.	Description of external SWOT analysis	67

1

Introduction

Representing and managing an enterprise architecture is challenging. Over the last few decades, the literature and practice have produced various frameworks and languages. Combining them into a holistic approach to derive the most benefit is the central research question of this master thesis. In addition, a prototype is created in the context of this paper so that this approach can be applied using a tool. This chapter describes the problem, the research questions based on it, and the structure of this thesis.

1.1. Problem Statement

Digitalization and the constant adaptation to changing market conditions have an impact on all elements of an enterprise's value creation: products and services, corporate capabilities and assets, alliances, partners, suppliers, and customers. Enterprises need to adapt and realign their corporate structure, processes, and information systems to the change [2].

To successfully manage change, the focus has increasingly been on enterprise architecture. In their explorative study, Hafsi and Assar have outlined the advantages of enterprise architecture, such as “increased responsiveness and flexibility (to change)” and “more effective use of IT resources” [16]. As the benefits of enterprise architecture have received more and more attention, the frameworks and methodologies around enterprise architecture have also evolved.

A common framework is The Open Group Architecture Framework (TOGAF) standard from The Open Group. It provides a best-practice approach with guidance and materials for efficient and effective use of enterprise architecture [40]. An important aspect of TOGAF is the consideration of the different architecture levels: Business Architecture, Information Systems Architectures, and Technology Architecture. All three levels are important for a holistic view of the company, but they differ in terms of processes, people involved, and technical characteristics. In terms of business architecture, for example, an application is viewed from a granular perspective, while in the technology architecture this application is viewed and documented in detail. The modeling languages also contribute to this important differentiation of levels.

The ArchiMate standard, also from The Open Group, accounts for these different levels, or, as they are also called, “business domains.” The standard provides a modeling language to analyze and visualize the architectures and the relationships between the domains [34]. However, other modeling languages are often more specific than ArchiMate and can be used to represent more details at the individual architectural levels and domains.

In practice, the challenge is to create a holistic and consistent architecture. To do this, the different layers and, if necessary, the different modeling languages must be related. Caetano et al. describe a way to use semantic techniques to model and analyze the ArchiMate, e3value, and Business Model Canvas modeling languages. They use the schema and transformation maps to relate the different elements of each modeling language across domains. However, their conclusion was that such a transformation map is always situation dependent [7]. In the approach of Lankhorst et al., ArchiMate is placed in the center and connected with other approaches and standards. This approach shows that a holistic architecture, which also corresponds to the TOGAF framework, can be achieved using a combination of several models [23].

In addition to the challenge of choosing the right framework and modeling languages, the appropriate tool must also be chosen. Gartner’s Magic Quadrant provides guidance for this. With their investigation and based on various evaluation criteria, they published an overview of the providers of Enterprise Architecture Management tools [37].

In the context of this work, further existing concepts and literature for a holistic modeling approach are collected and analyzed. Based on this, an approach is developed that includes the modeling languages ArchiMate, e3-Value, Business Process Model and Notation (BPMN) 2.0, and UML (Unified Modeling Language). Furthermore, a prototype is created on the open source platform ADOxx, which allows this approach to be applied.

1.2. Research Questions

The problem definition shows that enterprise architecture is an important topic and that much has already been accomplished in this area. In the context of this master thesis, the question is why enterprise architecture is necessary and why a holistic approach is important. These questions are mainly about combining different architecture disciplines and methods to generate value. Furthermore, a tool will be developed that can be used for this purpose, to train new professionals in this field, and to sensitize them to the topic. For this reason, the following three research questions were formulated and are addressed.

Question 1:

What does a holistic enterprise architecture contain, and what advantages does it offer?

There are various approaches to establishing a holistic enterprise architecture and a great deal of literature on it. The purpose of this paper is to describe the main aspects of enterprise architecture and to refer to the relevant frameworks and research papers. In addition, the main advantages of holistic enterprise architectures are discussed.

Question 2:**How can standardized and state-of-the-art modeling languages be combined?**

Based on the literature, this paper discusses the modeling languages ArchiMate, e3-Value, BPMN 2.0, and UML and describes how they can be combined. The paper shows the sub-discipline in which these architectures have their strengths as well as who uses them. Furthermore, the conclusion discusses how the approach could be further developed and, for example, how additional modeling languages could be included.

Question 3:**How can connections or interaction points between modeling languages be implemented in a modeling platform?**

With the findings from research question 2, the described modeling languages will be made available in a prototype implementation on the ADOxx platform. This should offer the possibility of performing modeling using the different languages and establishing a connection between them.

1.3. Structure of Work

After the problem definition and the research questions in Chapter 1, Chapter 2 describes the methodology used. In this master thesis, the design science research method was used. For this reason, the thesis is divided into four phases, which are also described in this chapter along with the methodological principles.

Chapter 3 discusses the basics of enterprise architecture. Here, the history is presented and the most important aspects such as existing frameworks, roles, and tools are described. This also addresses research question 1 to show the added value of enterprise architecture.

Chapter 4 provides theoretical basics about TOGAF and the modeling languages ArchiMate, e3-Value, BPMN 2.0, and UML, which are relevant for the approach developed in this thesis. The individual concepts and, in the case of the modeling languages, the most important elements are described. This chapter is intended to give the reader a brief overview of the modeling concepts and languages used. A detailed description is explicitly avoided here because the modeling languages are already thoroughly documented in the literature.

Chapter 5 describes the approach for a holistic enterprise architecture. The first section describes the connection of the partial architectures in the modeling languages e3-Value, BPMN 2.0, and UML to the overall architecture in the ArchiMate language. The second section explains how the sub-architectures can be connected.

Based on the approach from the chapter 5, the prototype is presented in Chapter 6. The ADOxx platform and its libraries are described, and the way in which the approach has been implemented in the platform is discussed.

Chapter 7 is dedicated to the evaluation according to the DSR methodology. For this purpose, an example is used to show the approach and application of the prototype. In addition, the approach and the prototype are evaluated with a SWOT Analysis.

Finally, Chapter 8 provides an outlook on possible further development. This offers concrete ideas on how the approach and the prototype could be extended.

2

Methodology

For the development of this master thesis and the resulting artifacts, a procedure based on the method for design science research (DSR) by Österle et al. was chosen [26] [27]. In addition, the guide by Benner-Wickner et al. was used [4].

The DSR method is well suited to investigate and solve a problem by creating an artifact. The advantage of this method is the close practical relevance. An important component of the method is the seven guidelines formulated by Hevner et al. in 2004 [18], listed in Table 1.

Principle	Description
Design as an Artifact	The goal is to create a real result/artifact that should achieve a practical use.
Problem Relevance	An existing problem must be addressed with the result.
Design Evaluation	The evaluation must show whether the problem could be solved with the result.
Research Contributions	Through the work, a generally valid research contribution is to be developed.
Research Rigor	Established methods must be applied correctly.
Design as a Search Process	Appropriate means must be used to achieve the desired goals within the constraints of the problem environment.
Communication of Research	The result and the research contribution must be published and made available.

Table 1.: Guiding principles of DSR according to Hevner et al. [4] [19]

In the context of this work, an attempt was made to always follow these guidelines. The approach to representing a holistic enterprise architecture and the prototype corresponds to guideline one. In the environment of open source modeling tools, ADOxx is a popular tool, especially for universities. However, there is currently no option to use different modeling languages in combination. This covers guidelines two and four. For the development of this master thesis and the resulting artifacts, care is taken to ensure that the methodological approach also complies with guidelines three, five, and six. The prototype and the approach for modeling a holistic enterprise architecture will be made available (guideline seven).

In addition to the guidelines of Henver et al., various phases are described in the context of DSR. In the diagram shown in Figure 1, the approach of Österle et al. [27] with the four phases — analysis, design, evaluation, and communication — can be seen. These four phases are also followed in the creation of this master thesis and the associated artifacts. The following sub-chapters briefly describe which results are developed in the corresponding phases.

Figure 1.: Overview of the methodology used; adapted from "Konsortialforschung, by Österle and Otto, 2010, *Wirtschaftsinformatik: Vol. 52, No. 5. Springer.* (S. 273-285)".[26]

2.1. Analysis

The first step in the analysis phase is to build up the knowledge base. For this purpose, an initial basic analysis was carried out in the first step using a proposal, and a plan for the work was made. Through literature research, various frameworks and concepts are analyzed to develop the knowledge base. Each finding from literature research as well as from practical experience is checked for its relevance to this work and then advanced to the next phase. This analysis and relevance check are iterative and need to be repeated in the next phases as new insights are gained.

In this first phase, research question one - what the purpose and goals of an enterprise architecture are and how they can be mapped - is already answered. In addition, the analysis phase forms the basis for research question two. With the knowledge base developed, the design phase can be started. The existing knowledge will also have to be expanded repeatedly in the next phases; thus, the basic knowledge must be supplemented by analyses.

2.2. Design

In the design phase according to DSR, the artifacts are created. As can be seen in Figure 1, in this thesis these artifacts are simultaneously the holistic approach (i.e., the underlying method) and the prototype with which this method can be applied.

The holistic approach is based on existing frameworks that were examined and evaluated in the analysis phase. To achieve the goals of this thesis, the relevant aspects must be taken over and supplemented accordingly. A method will be developed to illustrate how the different modeling languages can be connected, and the purpose of this will be described. Based on the developed method, the prototype will be created. For this purpose, the ADOxx platform and existing libraries on this platform will be reused. The prototype will be a new ADOxx library that will allow the proposed approach to be applied. For this purpose, the relevant components, such as elements, connectors and model types, must be taken over from existing libraries.

This will answer the second research question: which state-of-the-art modeling languages can be combined and the third research question: How can connections or interaction points between modeling languages be implemented in a modeling platform.

2.3. Evaluation

Evaluation is the third phase of the DSR method: the developed artifacts must be evaluated. In this thesis, this is done with a scenario-based evaluation and with a SWOT analysis (strengths, weaknesses, opportunities, and threats). In the evaluation, some models will be created and explained with the different modeling languages using an example. This should also serve as an aid for possible application, which is described in the last phase. The SWOT analysis provides an overview of why the holistic approach and created prototype should be used and what must be considered. It also describes possible further developments to make better use of strengths and opportunities and reduce weaknesses or threats.

2.4. Communication

The last phase shows how the created artifacts can be disseminated; for example, the library will be made available to the ADOxx community. This makes it possible to use the prototype and the associated method in education and training. The holistic enterprise architecture approach could also be published as a scientific paper; this would be done outside of this thesis.

3

Fundamentals of Enterprise Architecture Management

Architecture is fundamental concepts or properties of a system in its environment embodied in its elements, relationships, and in the principles of its design and evolution.

ISO/IEC/IEEE 42010:2011[1].

Enterprise architecture management (EAM) is an analysis, planning, and control tool that provides the basis for successful change or further development of an enterprise. It can be used to answer various questions and thus derive appropriate actions. The architecture provides information on the functional and technical characteristics of a company and its systems and describes their relation to one another. With an enterprise architecture, one thus obtains transparency about the business architecture and the information technology (IT) landscape. This allows IT solutions to be better aligned with the business, especially in today's world of rapid digital change [17].

There are many different definitions and explanations of enterprise architecture in the literature, and the difference between EAM and IT architecture management is sometimes challenging. The architecture pyramid according to G. Dern (Figure 2) illustrates the individual components of EAM.

Figure 2.: Architecture pyramid; in accordance with *Management von IT-Architekturen: Informationssysteme im Fokus von Architekturplanung und -entwicklung* by G. Dern, 2013,p.6. [9]

The strategy level describes the company's vision, goals, and strategy. An organization needs to adapt to market changes and align its processes, products, and resources accordingly. To this end, enterprise architecture strategy provides a roadmap and framework in the form of specifications, guidelines, and principles to align business processes and systems to achieve strategic goals. EAM is also a supplier of strategy. With EAM, the vision and the desired target image can be specified and mapped. Through appropriate evaluation and visualization, the architecture can help management make strategic decisions. A close link between strategy and enterprise architecture makes it possible to plan and develop a more efficient and effective enterprise design [17].

The business architecture then describes how to achieve the vision and goals of an organization as defined by the strategy level and the enterprise architecture; it does this by relating business capabilities, processes, and systems. This makes it easier to identify and address interdependencies and critical or rewarding business areas. The business architecture provides the basis for requirements management and the development of the IT landscape. According to Hanschke's EAM best practice approach, the business architecture can be divided into different dimensions, presented in Table 2 [17].

Dimension	Description
Business process	Business processes show how a company achieves its value creation. Processes have a clearly defined outcome and consist of activities and defined beginning and end.
Business capability	The capabilities of an organization, a person or a system are the means by which an organization tries to achieve its goals. Capabilities can be described by business functions and implemented by resources or technologies. A distinction is usually made between competitive differentiation and support functions.
Business ecosystem	The business ecosystem mainly contains information on suppliers, service providers, manufacturers, and processors as well as on other business partners, networks, and market partners. The ecosystem should be able to generate the greatest possible added value for customers and drive internal optimization and innovation. Cooperation with customers or competitors can also be described in this dimension.
Customers and touch points	This dimension describes customers, whether actual or potential. The touch points explain how customers come into contact with the company. This can be used to identify appropriate distribution channels.
Product	A product or sub-product is the result produced by a company through its processes and can be either tangible or intangible.
Business object	A business object is a functional term for abstract or concrete objects used in information processing.
Business entity	Logical or structural business units can be described in terms of business entities.

Table 2.: Dimensions of the Business Architecture [17]

The information architecture is the interface between the business architecture and the IT architecture. The information systems with their interfaces and the information objects are mapped at this level. Linking elements of the business architecture dimensions to the information systems provides a good overview of the IT landscape and the functions it performs. This can reveal missing IT support for processes or redundant functionality. To operate the information systems, however, a suitable IT architecture and operating infrastructure are required. These are the two lowest levels in Dern's pyramid. Platforms and tools for system management and development are mapped in the IT architecture. Furthermore, the technology stack and protocols are dealt with here. The main products in this architecture level are the reference architectures and integration architectures. These can provide specifications as well as patterns for how IT products such as information systems are implemented in the company. The operational infrastructure is a high-level description of infrastructure elements such as hardware components, data centres or networks. The Configuration Management Database (CMDB) is linked to this architectural layer. It maps the instantiation of infrastructure elements [17].

In practice, enterprise architecture is described by analogy with urban planning or building construction. In enterprise architecture, the city is planned and managed in its broad outlines. It therefore includes a general overview of the streets, buildings, and the institutions that are part of it. For example, in enterprise architecture, there might be several tramways running through the city, built and operated by the organization. This is then detailed, mapped and managed in the various sub-disciplines of enterprise architecture. Returning to the city example, the lowest level of the architecture pyramid is the tram routes. Each tram line is described, along with when it will be built, by which team in the organisation, and how its operation will be planned.

3.1. History of the Development

As early as 1987, Zachman described the growing importance of the architecture of information systems. His insight was that there is not just one architecture, but several - each representing a different point of view. The different architectures should be seen as additive and complementary. Zachman's model can be seen as the basis for many sub-sequent enterprise architecture frameworks and concepts. Many of the frameworks that have since been developed are heavily based on Zachman's foundations, and he is frequently mentioned in the enterprise architecture literature [17].

In the years that followed, another important enterprise architecture framework was established: The Open Group Architecture Framework (TOGAF). It is the result of a customer initiative and is based on the U.S. Department of Defense's Technical Architecture Framework for Information Management. It is a generic framework that can be used in conjunction with other frameworks and methodologies, depending on the sector/industry, to best meet business needs. It is therefore often referred to as an industry standard or best practice framework [40]. Initially, enterprise architecture was mainly used in the context of IT, but today it is used in a wide range of industries and does not refer only to IT. The representation and control of capabilities and processes in a holistic business context has become established.

3.2. The Purpose and Impact of an Enterprise Architecture

A holistic enterprise architecture has the advantage of considering all aspects of the enterprise and relating them to one another. This ensures that all areas of the company are aligned and in harmony. This makes it possible to design processes and systems more efficiently and to better align the company's business operations. It also helps minimize risks and enable the company to respond more quickly to change - all companies are subject to change and must adapt to the market. To successfully manage this change, both the current state and the desired target state must be understood. Examples of such a necessary change can be the digitalization of processes, the use of new technologies to increase efficiency or save costs, or the development of new business areas. Often several systems are involved, and many dependencies need to be considered. With the help of an enterprise architecture, complexity can be better managed and changes imple-

mented. However, an enterprise architecture should be used at an early stage to derive the greatest benefit from it. It helps stakeholders - especially management- gain a better understanding of the transformation and weigh the impact of their decisions.

Based on a literature and practice analysis, Aier, Riege, and Winter desired an overview of the state of the discipline of enterprise architecture in 2007. The literature analysis showed that the benefits of enterprise architecture lie mainly in documentation, planning and analysis, and business/IT integration and as a basis for decision making. The authors then conducted a nonrepresentative survey of practitioners that showed, for example, that business processes, interfaces, and products/services are important components of enterprise architecture. However, most enterprise architectures - 59% according to the survey - are still located in the IT department of a company. This, together with the assessment of the scope of the enterprise architecture, shows that the architecture is still shaped by IT, as was the case at the outset with Zachman [3].

Inge Hanschke makes a similar point in her book *Enterprise Architecture Management, Simple and Effective*. She sees the benefits differently, depending on the impact and time horizon. In the first phase, an enterprise architecture is used to create transparency between business and IT. This can be achieved with a simple process map or system list, for example. In particular, the aim is to provide decision-making aids and support for requirements elicitation. In the medium term, however, an enterprise architecture should generate concrete business value. This can be achieved, for example, through process analysis and automation or by combining IT systems with the same functionalities and capabilities. The alignment of business and IT with the business strategy is important here. The aim of enterprise architecture should be to enable long-term planning and control of the business. This is how the greatest value can be generated. Hanschke sees the advantage of enterprise architecture as flexibility, which, as mentioned, is extremely valuable in terms of being able to react quickly to changes in the market. This ability to react more quickly, together with the potential savings from optimizing IT, can provide a competitive advantage over the competition. An overview of the described advantages is shown in Figure 3 [17].

Figure 3.: Benefits of Enterprise Architecture Management; adapted from *Enterprise Architecture Management. Einfach und Effektiv*, by Hanschke Inge, 2022, (S. 194) [17]

However, enterprise architecture can have disadvantages - in particular, building a holistic architecture in an existing organization requires much initial effort. When architecture components need to be redocumented, it is often difficult to find the right documentation and the right stakeholders and then to ensure that the information is still up to date and accurate. Maintaining the architecture can quickly become very time consuming and costly due to its complexity. Table 3 gives a short list and description of possible disadvantages of a holistic enterprise architecture; these will be different in each organization, and there may be others.

Disadvantage	Description
Costs	A comprehensive view of all aspects of the business can lead to higher costs because more time and resources are required for planning and implementation.
Complexity	A holistic approach can add complexity to the organization's processes and systems, making them more difficult to manage.
Flexibility	A heavy reliance on architecture can reduce the flexibility of the organization because changes to one part of the architecture can affect other areas.
Missing focus	An overly broad architecture can cause an organization to lose focus on its core competencies and goals.
Challenging implementation	A holistic enterprise architecture requires a comprehensive knowledge of all aspects of the enterprise and can therefore be difficult to implement.

Table 3.: Disadvantages of a holistic Enterprise Architecture [17]

Therefore, it is important for an organization to consider whether and how to establish an enterprise architecture. It is often difficult for non-IT management to see the benefits of an architecture. In the beginning, an enterprise architecture may be costly and add little value; however, in the long term, savings can be realized. The advantages and disadvantages of enterprise architecture need to be weighed and clearly explained, but the organization must be prepared to make the initial effort to reap the benefits. In her book, Hanschke describes a best-practice approach to EAM and recommends not starting with the entire complexity, but rather building the architecture step by step. The goals of the stakeholders and the benefits they receive from the architecture should be considered; this will help determine whether the benefits and costs are appropriately balanced. An appropriate EAM framework can be used for this purpose because it often provides possible arguments and examples of the benefits of the architecture. This can give stakeholders a sense of possible usage and collaboration [17].

Practical experience shows that even simple products from the architecture can have an impact and obtain stakeholder support. This is crucial because without executive commitment and stakeholder cooperation, an architecture can quickly become outdated and contain incomplete information.

3.3. Roles in Enterprise Architecture

When a company reaches a certain size and complexity, it becomes difficult to have the entire architecture managed by a single person or role. Specialization and division of tasks are required. Thus, in recent years, various job profiles and roles have also been developed for the specialized discipline of architecture. Wissotzki, Köpp, and Stelzer have created a grouping of roles in the area of EAM with the help of a literature search [31]. Table 4 shows some of their findings regarding the roles and their tasks.

Role	Description
Enterprise Architect	Responsible for the completeness and quality of the architecture across divisions and in terms of business strategy. Identifies synergies between sub-architectures (business, information, and technology architecture) and reviews solution architectures and transformations with respect to the overall architecture.
Business Architect	Responsible for the design, documentation, and further development of the business architecture as well as business processes.
Information Architect	Responsible for the design, documentation and further development of the Information Architecture. Responsible for the data model and reviews where business objects are created and processed in the system.
Application Architect	Responsible for the company's application landscape. Must ensure documentation of applications and address the relevant stakeholders.
Infrastructure Architecture	Responsible for the IT infrastructure with its technologies, services, and operating systems. Has an overview of the system architectures and brings these architectures into operation or projects.
Solution Architect	Responsible for planning concrete solutions for projects or changes. To do this, the solution architect uses information from all sub-areas of architecture and works with other architects.

Table 4.: Roles in enterprise architecture [31]

A company does not need to have every role filled; in smaller companies, it makes sense to combine certain functions. For example, the business architect can also take on the role of the enterprise architect and be more responsible for the business side, and there may be an information architect who takes care of all the IT. In larger organizations, it makes sense to have several solution architects because they are often involved in projects.

Other roles are relevant to the architecture because they are involved as suppliers of information or as users of the architecture. Project managers need to incorporate the architecture and are responsible for ensuring that projects are aligned with it. At the beginning of a project, this is more likely to be a collaboration with the business architect; in the development and implementation phase, this is more likely a collaboration with the solution architect. IT Operations and Service Management in an organization tend to work with the information, application, and infrastructure architects. This is where ongoing operational changes need to be mapped and planned for.

3.4. Enterprise Architecture Tools

Because enterprise architecture, even in smaller organizations, can quickly grow to include many elements and thus increase in complexity, tool support is essential. In addition to effective architecture governance, tools are needed to enable the various roles in the architecture discipline to work together. It is most important that architecture data be kept complete, consistent, and up to date. A poorly maintained database runs the risks of decisions being made based on incorrect assumptions and of the organization failing to achieve its goals. When it comes to making decisions or answering stakeholder questions, enterprise architecture provides a valuable contribution. Through key performance indicators (KPIs), dashboards, or reports, relationships and information can be prepared and presented in a way that is easy to interpret. With appropriate tool support, such representations are also reproducible and repeatable, supporting traceability and development analysis.

In recent years, various enterprise architecture management tools have been established on the market; these tools have different strengths and weaknesses. An overview of the leading EAM tools can be found in the Gartner Magic Quadrant; in addition, Gartner offers a review rating of the EA tools on the market [37]. Well-known EAM tools include ADOIT, LeanIX Enterprise Architecture Suite, Alfabet, and Sparx Systems Enterprise Architect. A further list of possible EAM tools can be found in the book *Enterprise Architecture Management* by Inge Hanschke in Chapter 6.2 [17].

4

Existing Modeling Concepts

This chapter introduces existing, relevant enterprise architecture frameworks and modeling concepts. First, a methodology for implementing enterprise architectures is defined and then the TOGAF framework is described in more detail. Then, the concept of modeling languages and the three state-of-the-art methods ArchiMate, e3-Value BPMN 2.0 and UML are explained. The methods are briefly introduced and the most important components are described.

4.1. Enterprise Architecture Implementation Methodologies

The Enterprise Architecture Implementation Methodology (EAIM) provides the framework and methods for developing and managing an enterprise architecture. It also provides the structure and constraints required for each of the sub-disciplines of enterprise architecture.

In recent years, several EAIMs have been developed and described by both academics and practitioners. The most frequently mentioned EAIMs in the literature [29] are as follows:

- The Open Group Architectural Framework (TOGAF)
- Department of Defense Architectural Framework (DoDAF)
- Enterprise Architecture Planning (EAP)
- Federal Enterprise Architecture (FEA)

In their article, Nikpay et al. describe two types of EAIMs: EAIMs that are implemented using an enterprise architecture framework, such as TOGAF, and EAIMs that are developed independently of a framework, such as EAP. This distinction can play a role in building an enterprise architecture because one type may be more appropriate depending on the skills and subject matter experts available. A common feature of all EAIMs is the concepts of transition from current to target state [25]. These concepts also provide the basis for the strategic benefits of enterprise architecture.

In the context of this thesis and the proposal for a holistic enterprise architecture, the EAIM TOGAF is used. This framework has been proven in practice and offers detailed documentation that can be used as a guide.

4.1.1. The Open Group Architecture Framework (TOGAF)

TOGAF is an enterprise architecture management framework that helps organizations design, monitor, and revise their business, information, and technology architecture. Originally developed by the U.S. Department of Defense, the framework has been managed and developed by The Open Group since the 2000s.

The framework provides an integrated view of business, information, and technology architecture that enables organizations to better align their business needs, technology resources, and IT systems. In addition, TOGAF defines standardized processes for architecture development and assessment, making it easier for organizations to design their architectures consistently and effectively. Such standardized processes and a common framework strengthen collaboration among business units, IT departments, and external partners by creating a common language and understanding of enterprise architecture.

The TOGAF library is a central component of the TOGAF framework and contains all the relevant documents, models, templates, and tools required to implement EAM. The library provides a comprehensive catalogue of all the artifacts needed to develop and manage business, information, and technology architectures. It also includes the standardized process descriptions and work instructions as well as examples ranging from architecture models and metamodels to templates and checklists for architecture assessment [40]. TOGAF also provides a structured definition of the organization, roles, skills, and responsibilities with its architecture capability framework. This allows the requirements of different stakeholders to be identified and addressed [17]. The TOGAF library thus provides architects with comprehensive support to ensure that all the necessary steps are taken to design a successful enterprise architecture. The full documentation scope of the current version of TOGAF is shown in Figure 4.

Figure 4.: TOGAF Documentation Set; reprinted from <https://pubs.opengroup.org/togaf-standard/introduction/chap02.html>, by The Open Group, 2022,[40]

One of the key components of the framework is the TOGAF architecture development method (ADM). The ADM cycle describes the steps that architects must take to develop and manage effective business, information, and technology architectures. It enables organizations to align their IT systems with business needs and ensure that their architectures are effective and efficient. The cycle consists of several phases that should be approached iteratively. Each phase describes how the individual and specific architecture components should be defined and implemented in the context of an overall enterprise architecture and addresses the different architectural characteristics and the roles involved in EAM [40]. Figure 5 shows the ADM cycle graphically, and Table 5 describes the individual phases. For further information, a review of the TOGAF specification is recommended.

Figure 5.: Architecture Development Cycle; reprinted from <https://pubs.opengroup.org/togaf-standard/introduction/chap02.html>, by The Open Group, 2022,[40]

Phase	Description
Preliminary	Preparation activities to get architecture capability, customization framework, and definition of architecture principles.
A: Architecture Vision	Definition of architecture development initiatives and architecture vision, identify stakeholders, and obtain approval for architecture development.
B: Business Architecture	Description of the development of a business architecture based on the strategy and architecture vision.
C: Information System Architectures	Description of the development of information system architectures based on the business architecture.
D: Technology Architectures	Description of the development of technology architectures with specifications of the business and information system architecture.
E: Opportunities & Solutions	Initial implementation planning of the architectures from the previous phases.
F: Migration Planning	Preparation of a detailed implementation and migration plan and description of the transition from the baseline to the target architecture.
G: Implementation Governance	Architectural oversight of the implementation.
H: Architecture Change Management	Description of the procedure for managing changes to the architecture and initializing changes due to new business requirements.
Requirements Management	Management of architectural requirements throughout the ADM cycle.

Table 5.: Description of the ADM cycle [40]

TOGAF does not have specific requirements for the modeling language for each phase of ADM. However, a decision should be made in the Preliminary Phase of TOGAF regarding which language(s) should be used to model the architecture. In addition, the underlying metamodel should be defined. A core enterprise metamodel is provided at the Foundation level in the TOGAF library.

According to TOGAF, another important component of an enterprise architecture is the architecture repository. This repository is where the architecture artifacts of the individual architectures are stored and made available to the stakeholders, and it contains the metamodel, the architecture landscapes, and various libraries. In the first ADM phases, this repository should be set up and the rules and standards for it defined [40].

4.2. State-of-the-art Modeling methods

Karagiannis and Kühn have described and graphically illustrated the components of modeling methods (see Figure 6). From their perspective, a modeling method consists of two main components: 1) modeling technique and 2) mechanisms and algorithms. The modeling technique is further divided into modeling language and modeling procedure. In the modeling procedures, mechanisms and algorithms can be used to evaluate the modeling language. The procedure describes the steps that must be taken when using the modeling language in order to obtain results. A model is then described with the modeling language either graphically or textually. This description includes the syntax, which forms the grammar of the modeling language; the semantics describe the meaning; and the notation provides the rules regarding visualization [21].

Figure 6.: Components of modeling methods; reprinted from *Proceedings of the Third International Conference EC-Web* (p. 182), by D. Karagiannis and H. Kühn, 2002, Springer [21]

In the following sub-chapters, the state-of-the-art modeling methods relevant for this work are presented. The modeling methods are not changed in the context of this work; rather, they are connected with one another. For this reason, a description of the modeling procedures and the mechanism is omitted. The focus is instead on the modeling language component because this is relevant for understanding the interdependencies and the representation in the prototype.

4.2.1. ArchiMate

ArchiMate is a modeling language for describing architectures and is an open standard from The Open Group. ArchiMate describes the concepts of the different architectural layers, which are also used in TOGAF. These two frameworks are aligned. Because ArchiMate is an accepted standard in practice and is widely used, there are several best-practice approaches and much documentation. Furthermore, models can be easily compared and

linked across organizations. In addition, ArchiMate is already implemented in many architecture tools, making it easy to switch from a simple tool such as ADOxx to a more expensive and complex architecture tool such as Sparx Enterprise Architect or ADOIT. The ArchiMate core framework (see Figure 7) consists of nine cells, which are used to classify the elements. In ArchiMate Full Framework version 3.1, the core framework has been extended with the strategy layer, implementation and migration layer, and the motivation aspect [34]. However, in this work only the ArchiMate core framework is worked; a possible extension to the full framework is described in Chapter 8.

Figure 7.: ArchiMate Core Framework; reprinted from <https://www.opengroup.org/archimate-forum/archimate-overview>, by The Open Group, 2022 [34]

Layers of the ArchiMate core framework are described in Table 6.

Layer	Description
Business Layer	The services offered to customers are modeled in the business layer. This also includes the business processes and actors that use these services.
Application Layer	The application layer represents the application services that support the enterprise and the applications that implement them.
Technology Layer	The technology layer represents technology services such as processing, storage, and communication services needed to run the applications as well as the computer and communication hardware and system software that implement these services. In addition, there are elements in this layer for modeling physical devices, materials, and distribution networks.

Table 6.: ArchiMate Layers of the Core Framework [34]

Aspects of the ArchiMate core framework are described in Table 7.

Aspects	Description
Active Structure	Representation of structure elements and actual behavior of business actors, application components, and devices.
Behavior	Representation of the behavior of processes, functions, events, and services executed by actors. Structure elements are mapped to behavior elements.
Passive Structure	Representation of the objects that are affected by the behavior. Most often, these are information objects of the business layer and data objects of the application layer but can also be physical objects.

Table 7.: ArchiMate Aspects of the Core Framework [34]

However, the classification of elements is not to be considered strictly but rather as a global classification. This is because real architectural elements can combine different aspects and thus can appear in multiple layers and aspects. Figure 8 shows the elements from the previously described layers and aspects.

	Structural Concepts				Behavioral Concepts				Informational Concepts	
Business	Business actor		Business role		Business process		Business service		Representation	Product
	Business collaboration		Business interface		Business function		Business event		Meaning	Contract
	Location		Business object		Business interaction				Value	
Application	Application component		Application collaboration		Application function		Application interaction			
	Application interface		Data object		Application service					
Technology	Node		Device		Infrastructure function		Infrastructure service		Artifact	
	Network		System software							
	Communication path		Infrastructure interface							

Figure 8.: ArchiMate Core Elements; reprinted from

<https://www.opengroup.org/archimate-forum/archimate-overview>, by The Open Group, 2022 [34]

4.2.2. e3-Value Method

Gordijn and Akkermans have developed a method for representing e-business models that shows how economic value is created and exchanged within a network of stakeholders. The graphical approach can be used to represent cross-enterprise relationships as well as the business requirements that must be met by IT systems and networks. The author

starts from three viewpoints: the business value viewpoint (focus on values, actors, and exchanges); the business process viewpoint (focus on processes, workers, information, goods, and control flows); and the system architecture viewpoint (focus on hardware/software components, data and control flows, and code organization) [15]. For the process and system architecture, UML should be used; for the business viewpoint, the e3-Value method should be used. The e3-Value approach provides the following benefits: 1) better communication and decision making about the fundamentals of an e-business model by stakeholders and 2) a sharper and more complete understanding of e-business operations and requirements up-front through scenario analysis and quantification [15].

The elements described in Table 8 are used in the e3-Value method and the Figure 9 shows the interaction of the elements.

Element	Description
Actor	Independent, economic (and often legal) entity. By performing value activities, the actor generates profit or increased utility.
Value Object	Service, product, money, or a consumer experience. Is of value for one or more actors and is exchanged.
Value Port	In this way, the actor indicates that it wants to provide or request a value object. Shows how to involve external actors and other components in the e-business model.
Value Interface	Grouping of value ports. Indicates which value objects an actor is willing to exchange for another via its ports. The exchange of value object instances is done atomically at the value interface level.
Value Exchange	Connects two value ports to one another. This can be used to represent one or more potential exchanges of value objects between value ports.
Value Offering	A set of value exchanges that shows the value exchanges of value objects. It should match the semantics of the connected value interfaces; i.e., values are exchanged across a value interface on all its ports or on no ports at all.
Market segment	A concept that divides a market, which consists of actors, into segments with common properties. A market segment indicates which actors use the same decision functions of a value interface.
Composite Actor	Shows a partnership of different actors jointly offering value objects.
Value Activity	Performed by actors to make profit or increase benefits. With inclusion in the ontology, the assignment to actors can be discussed and designed.

Table 8.: e3-Value Method: Elements [15, 28]

Figure 9.: e3-Value Method; reprinted from "e3-value: Design and Evaluation of e-Business Models" by Jaap Gordijn and Hans Akkermans, 2001, *IEEE Intelligent Systems*, 16(4)[15]

Modeling Approach for Blockchain-inspired Business Models (MABBM)

Blockchain technology has become increasingly important in recent years, and new business models have developed as a result. In his master thesis, Simon Perrelet has designed a modeling method that allows such business models to be represented. The method is based on the established e3-Value method. Perrelet has extended the existing elements with additional attributes and functions (see Table 9) [28].

Element	Description
DAO	Construct built on blockchain technology. In DAOs, management programs its governance rules and decision-making processes in smart contracts.

Table 9.: Extension MABBM [28]

4.2.3. BPMN 2.0

Every organization has processes that need to be managed and considered within the enterprise architecture. There are already many different frameworks, methods, and modeling languages for business process management (BPM) in the literature and in practice. In recent years, the Business Process Model and Notation (BPMN) method from the Object Management Group (OMG) has established itself as a standard, is driven by industry, and is now listed by ISO. Because of its familiarity and widespread use, BPMN 2.0 offers the advantage of facilitating communication about processes between different experts. Because BPMN 2.0 is also well established in education and research,

specialists are already being trained in this standard, and new solutions are constantly being developed in the context of this standard. This is one reason there are many BPMN 2.0 modeling tools on the market, some of which are free. Although BPMN 2.0 has many different elements, it is often easy to understand due to its symbolism and visualization. This makes it possible to discuss processes outside of IT. In addition, since version 2.0, it has been possible to execute process models directly using process engines. This brings significant benefits in terms of digitization and automation. However, care must be taken to ensure that process modeling is semantically and syntactically correct, even if the business reader understands the process with little knowledge, otherwise, IT may implement something incorrectly. Freund and Rucker see this as the challenge for a process architect or process manager [14].

Table 10 shows the main elements of BPMN 2.0. There are other variants - especially for activity, event, and gateways - which can be read in the OMG specification.

Element	Description
Event	Represents an event in the process that triggers something or shows a result (start, intermediate event, or end).
Activity	Represents the individual steps that a company performs.
Gateway	Used to control the process flows. It shows the branching, forking, and merging of paths.
Pool	Represents a participant in a collaboration or process.
Lane	A sub-partition within a process or pool; used to organize and categorize activities.
Data Object	Inputs to activities and/or what they produce.
Message	Represents the content of a communication between two participants.
Group	Enables graphical grouping of elements of the same category.
Text Annotation	Allows the capture of additional notes.
Sequence Flow	Shows the order of the activities.
Message Flow	Show the flow of the messages.
Association	Allows the linking of information and artifacts to the elements.

Table 10.: BPMN 2.0 basic modeling elements [36]

The most commonly used diagram in BPMN 2.0 is the business process diagram, which shows the flow of a single process. If communication with other processes and partners outside the own process is shown, the diagram illustrates collaboration. There is also the conversation diagram, which deals specifically with communication between different partners, and the choreography diagram, which views the process from a global perspective [14].

4.2.4. UML

Originally, the Unified Modeling Language (UML) was synthesized from different object-oriented methods, in particular to achieve stability and standardization in software design [5]. Since 1997, OMG has been managing and further developing the modeling language UML. Using UML, structures and designs of software systems can be visualized and documented using a model. In the field of software modeling and IT, UML is the standard and is also well suited to represent object-oriented concepts and thus support development and coding with object-oriented languages. With UML 2.0, 13 standard diagrams and elements are available, which can be used according to the specific purpose (see Figure 10) [41].

Figure 10.: UML 2.0 diagrams; reprinted from "www.omg.org/spec/UML/2.5/PDF", by Object Management Group, 2022,[41]

5

Solution Approach for Holistic Enterprise Architecture Modeling

In previous chapters, the value of several standard modeling languages was shown. In the following, an approach is presented that offers a possibility to create a holistic enterprise architecture and use the advantages of the individual modeling languages. ArchiMate is used as the main modeling language for enterprise architecture. In principle, it can be used to model the entire ADM cycle according to TOGAF. If more detailed architecture models are required, the modeling languages e3-Value or MABBM, BPMN 2.0, and UML can be used and linked to the overall architecture in the ArchiMate language. This allows each architecture role involved to work in its preferred modeling language and still results in an overall and consistent model.

There is also the possibility to refer with links within the different modeling languages between elements and models. In this way, the modeling languages e3-Value, BPMN 2.0, and UML can be connected. However, these references have very weak semantics and indicate that only a loose connection exists.

5.1. Holistic Enterprise Architecture Model

The following holistic approach was developed as part of this master thesis and serves as the basis for the development of the prototype on the ADOxx platform. It shows how the specific and more detailed modeling languages e3-Value/MABBM, BPMN 2.0, and UML can be connected to the overall architecture in ArchiMate. This approach includes only the most important connections, some of which have already been described by Lankhorst et al. [23]. An extension of the model is described in Chapter 8.

In Figures 11, 12, 13, the approach for the holistic overall model is shown divided according to the three ArchiMate layers. The connections show which elements from the more detailed modeling languages e3-Value, BPMN 2.0, and UML are represented by which ArchiMate elements in the enterprise architecture. An explanation of the connections and the elements involved is given from Section 5.1.1. No cardinalities are explicitly shown here because this depends on the tool used. If a database is used to create the architectures in which individual elements can always be reused, there should be a 1:1 relationship between the model in ArchiMate and the other models. However, if the same element must be modeled several times, a multiple connection is also possible so that all

identical elements in a more detailed modeling language refer to the same element in the enterprise architecture - for example, in the enterprise architecture, a certain event is modeled once; in the detailed modeling with BPMN 2.0, it is used and modeled in five processes. Thus, all five elements representing the identical event should refer to the ArchiMate element.

Figure 11.: References to the ArchiMate Business Layer

Figure 12.: References to the ArchiMate Application Layer

Figure 13.: References to the ArchiMate Technology Layer

5.1.1. ArchiMate and e3-Value

The e3-Value method allows business models to be presented in more detail. In particular, more complex ecosystems and their actors can be mapped and thus the entire value creation can be represented. The insights gained from this modeling support the formulation of necessary requirements for the information layer and technology layer [28]. Although the e3-Value modeling language is more abstract and generic than the ArchiMate language, there are approaches on how to combine the two languages or use them individually instead. Engelsman, Wilco, et al. in their article "Transforming e3-Value models into ArchiMate diagrams" hypothesize the transformation of e3-Value models into ArchiMate models. After a more detailed investigation, they established guidelines for the transformation. According to their guidelines, the connection and transformation between e3-Value and ArchiMate's strategic and business layer can be established [11].

The following table 12 shows which e3-Value elements are represented by which ArchiMate elements. A short definition of the elements is also given.

ArchiMate	e3-Value
<p>Business actor <i>A business actor represents a business entity that can carry out a behavior.</i></p>	<p>Actor <i>An actor is an economic unit. An actor performs value activities that best increase utility and generate profit.</i></p>
<p>Business role <i>A business role is responsible for a specific action or behavior and is assigned to an actor.</i></p>	<p>Actor <i>An actor is an economic unit. An actor performs value activities that best increase utility and generate profit.</i></p>
<p>Business service <i>A business service is provided by a business role, business actor, or business collaboration of its environment.</i></p>	<p>Value activity <i>A value activity is carried out by an actor and increases that actor's profit/utility.</i></p>
<p>Business interface <i>A Business Interface is used to make the business services available to the environment.</i></p>	<p>Value activity <i>A value activity is carried out by an actor and increases that actor's profit/utility.</i></p>
<p>Business collaboration <i>A Business Collaboration is an aggregate of two or more active structural elements within a business that work together to perform a collective behavior.</i></p>	<p>Value interface <i>The actors have one or multiple interfaces that summarize the individual value interfaces. This shows which value objects an actor wants to exchange for other value objects through its ports.</i></p>

Table 12.: ArchiMate [34] and e3-Value [15]

In the context of this prototype, ArchiMate's strategic layer is excluded and thus only guidelines G5–G12 are relevant to the prototype and holistic approach. For the application of the two modeling languages in a holistic approach, consulting the guidelines is recommended.

5.1.2. ArchiMate and BPMN 2.0

In this approach, ArchiMate can be used to represent the higher level processes and their dependencies in the organization. This makes it possible to create a process map at the enterprise architecture level. This map shows the enterprise architect, the business architect, and which processes are available in the company to create the products or support the value chain.

The modeling language BPMN 2.0 is mainly used for the detailed mapping of processes [23]. Compared to ArchiMate modeling, with BPMN 2.0 it is possible to show in detail which objects are produced or used in which activities. In the overall architecture, it is shown only that these are related to the process. In addition, events can be represented in more detail using the BPMN 2.0 modeling language, e.g., message events or timer events.

Overall, this methodology provides the enterprise architecture and business architecture roles and the (business) process manager with a familiar and suitable tool. In particular, the process manager has additional possibilities for automating processes with the BPMN 2.0 modeling language, which are less available with the ArchiMate modeling language. The elements of the two modeling languages to be linked are shown in Table 14.

ArchiMate	BPMN 2.0
<p>Business process <i>A business process is a sequence of business actions that produces a specific result, such as products or business services.</i></p>	<p>BusinessProcess <i>A series of business activities that represent the steps required to achieve a business goal. These also include the flow and use of information and resources.</i></p>
<p>Business event <i>A business event represents a change in the state of an organization.</i></p>	<p>StartEvent, IntermediateEvent or EndEvent <i>An event represents an occurrence during a process or choreography and influences the flow of the model. Events usually have a cause (trigger) or an effect (outcome). There are three types of events: start, intermediate, and end.</i></p>
<p>Business actor <i>A business actor represents a business entity that can carry out a behavior.</i></p>	<p>Pool or Lane <i>A pool represents a participant in a process or collaboration. It serves as a graphical container for the activities. A lane represents a sub-area within a process or a pool.</i></p>
<p>Business object <i>A business object represents a concept that is used within a particular area of the business.</i></p>	<p>DataObject <i>Data objects give information about what is executed in activities and what they produce.</i></p>
<p>Application service <i>An application service represents an exposed application functionality that has been expressly defined.</i></p>	<p>Pool or Lane <i>A pool represents a participant in a process or collaboration. It serves as a graphical container for the activities. A participant in a process can also be an application or a service. Accordingly, the activities are performed by the system. A lane represents a sub-area within a process or a pool.</i></p>
<p>Application process <i>An application process is a sequence of application actions that work together to produce a particular outcome.</i></p>	<p>BusinessProcess <i>A set of activities that are the steps required to achieve a desired state. This includes the flow and use of information and resources.</i></p>

ArchiMate	BPMN 2.0
<p>Application event</p> <p><i>An application event represents a change in application state.</i></p>	<p>StartEvent, IntermediateEvent or EndEvent</p> <p><i>An event represents an occurrence during a process or choreography and influences the flow of the model. Events usually have a cause (trigger) or an effect (outcome). There are three types of events: start, intermediate, and end.</i></p>
<p>Data object</p> <p><i>A data object is a representation of data in a form suitable for computer processing.</i></p>	<p>DataObject</p> <p><i>Data objects give information about what is executed in activities and what they produce.</i></p>
<p>Technology process</p> <p><i>A technology process is a sequence of technology activities performed to achieve an outcome.</i></p>	<p>Business Process</p> <p><i>A set of activities that are the steps required to achieve a desired state. This includes the flow and use of information and resources.</i></p>
<p>Technology event</p> <p><i>A technology event represents a change in the state of a technology.</i></p>	<p>StartEvent, IntermediateEvent or EndEvent</p> <p><i>An event represents an occurrence during a process or choreography and influences the flow of the model. Events usually have a cause (trigger) or an effect (outcome). There are the three types of events, which can be further specified: Start, Intermediate and End.</i></p>

Table 14.: ArchiMate [34] and BPMN 2.0 [36]

5.1.3. ArchiMate and UML

Particularly for the architectures of the application and technology layers, or in the case of phases C and D of TOGAF, it is recommended to model the architectures with UML in addition to ArchiMate. UML is mainly used in software development to support the design and development process. Application and infrastructure architecture specialists and solution architects are familiar with this modeling language. In ArchiMate modeling, the same could be represented to a certain extent, but in this approach, too, it is recommended to remain only coarsely granular. In the enterprise architecture, only the most important technical processes, artifacts, components etc. and their relationships and dependencies should be shown. Table 16 shows the connections between ArchiMate and UML.

ArchiMate	UML
Application service <i>An application service represents an exposed application functionality that has been expressly defined.</i>	Actor <i>An actor specifies a role of a user or a system interacting with the subject.</i>
Application collaboration <i>An application collaboration is an aggregate of at least two active internal structure elements of an application that work together to perform collective application action.</i>	Collaboration <i>A collaboration represents a set of collaborating elements (roles), each of which performs a particular function, and which work together to achieve a desired functionality.</i>
Application component <i>An application component is a modular, replaceable encapsulation of application functionality that is aligned with implementation structure.</i>	Component <i>A component is a system's modular component. Within its surroundings, it is interchangeable and encapsulates its contents.</i>
Application process <i>An application process is a sequence of application actions that work together to produce a particular outcome.</i>	Use Case <i>A Use Case is a behavior specification. An occurrence of the emergent behavior that corresponds to the associated Use Case is referred to as an instance of a Use Case. Interactions frequently provide descriptions of such events.</i>
Data object <i>A data object is a representation of data in a form suitable for computer processing.</i>	Class <i>A class allows for the specification of object classifications and the capture of features that disclose an object's characteristics in terms of structure and behavior.</i>

ArchiMate	UML
<p>Node <i>A node represents a computational or physical resource hosting, manipulating or interacting with other computational or physical resources.</i></p>	<p>Node <i>Nodes are an elaboration and specification of the abstract notion of deployment targets. They can be nested and interconnected through communication paths to form systems of any complexity. Typically, a node represents either a hardware device or a software execution environment.</i></p>
<p>Artifact <i>An artifact is a piece of data used in a software development process or produced by the deployment and operation of an IT system.</i></p>	<p>Artefact <i>An artefact is an often tangible piece of information used or produced by a software development process or system operation.</i></p>
<p>Technology process <i>A technology process is a sequence of technology activities performed to achieve an outcome.</i></p>	<p>Use Case <i>A use case is a behavior specification. An occurrence of the emergent behavior that corresponds to the associated use case is referred to as an "instance of a use case." Interactions frequently provide descriptions of such events.</i></p>

Table 16.: ArchiMate [34] and UML [41]

5.2. Links Between the Modeling Languages

In addition to the statement describing how elements are represented in the overall architecture, it is necessary in practice to be able to create a further connection between individual architectural elements. To achieve this, in this proposed approach, a linking among the modeling languages e3-Value, BPMN 2.0, and UML is suggested. This approach is first implemented as a loose coupling of elements. This means that no further statements can be made about the linkage of two elements. It only supports the modelers in recognizing and storing a connection to other models. A possible extension of this loose coupling is described in Chapter 8.

5.2.1. e3-Value and BPMN 2.0

The modeling language e3-Value is well suited to express which value is exchanged between different actors, and the language BPMN 2.0 shows how this happens. Thus, a link between these two models is a good idea. Torres, Gordijn, Fantinato, and Vieira have hypothesized in their paper "Designing an Ecosystem Value Model Based on a Process Model - An Empirical Approach" how the two modeling languages correspond and have tested them with a real use case [30]. One insight gained is that some information can be lost by transforming from one model to another because, for example, in BPMN 2.0, actors are represented with very little information and detail. For this reason, this approach recommends not to make a transformation but rather to map the two models and

languages as a complement to one another. With a link between the models, additional information can be gained.

5.2.2. e3-Value and UML

Huemer et al. consider that business models are an important component in the development and adaptation of information systems and should also be available in UML, the standard language of software engineering. For this reason, in their paper "A UML Profile for the e3-Value e-Business Model Ontology", they have developed possible approaches for mapping business models based on the e3-Value notation into the UML language. From their point of view there are four possible approaches with the activity diagram and one with the use case diagram of UML. Using an example, they explain in the paper which elements in UML correspond to those of e3-Value and how the diagram should be modelled. Their conclusion that the UML diagrams must be understandable to experts with little knowledge of the notation and that the diagrams must not be overloaded fits the approach proposed in this thesis. The e3-Value model should be created for the business people and by using UML the business model can be represented for the more technical specialists. With a link between the models, it is possible to refer to the other model and react more quickly to changes [20].

5.2.3. BPMN 2.0 and UML

Especially between the two UML diagrams - activity diagram and sequence diagram - and a BPMN 2.0 process diagram, connections can occur that may describe the same process from a different point of view and with a different focus. A link between the elements or the diagrams is recommended so that technical adjustments or further developments are aligned with the business and its processes.

There are also some approaches to transform BPMN 2.0 models into use case diagrams in the literature. Cruz et al. have examined some concepts in their paper and presented an approach themselves. In particular, they transform information from the BPMN 2.0 process into the description of a use case because more details are visible in a process at first glance than in a use case diagram [8]. With the approach proposed here, it should not be possible to make a transformation but rather a link. Thus, it is possible to jump from a use case to a more detailed process and obtain more information if needed.

Another possible use case for a link between the two modeling languages occurs when a data object from a business process is to be specified in more detail and, above all, technically. A link can then be made from the data object to a class, an artifact, or a component. Figure 14 shows the recommended and most common dependencies between the various elements.

Figure 14.: Links between BPMN 2.0 and UML

6

Prototype of a Modeling Toolkit for a Holistic Enterprise Architecture

As a tool for creating a holistic enterprise architecture, a prototype is created on the ADOxx modeling platform. This prototype contains the modeling languages described in Chapter 5, which have been imported into ADOxx as libraries. In the course of this work, the libraries will be interconnected and, if necessary, extended to implement the holistic approach.

6.1. ADOxx

ADOxx is a metamodeling platform from the nonprofit organization Open Model Initiative Laboratory (OMiLAB). ADOxx is a development and configuration platform for the implementation of modeling languages and tools. In a development environment, modeling languages can be configured and implemented, and scripting approaches can be used to store executable functionality such as simulations and queries. The platform also includes other valuable features such as user management, import/export transformations, and add-on implementations. This enables the rapid development of professional modeling tools [38].

ADOxx is based on the metamodel approach with different languages and roles. This allows multiple modeling languages and models to be mapped on the platform. A “metamodel” is the representation of the abstract syntax of the modeling language, and a “model” is the representation of its concrete syntax. It is also possible to describe the metamodel, which is then called the metamodeling language. The representation of the concrete syntax of the metamodeling language is then called a “meta² model”. This hierarchy, as well as the roles and technical implementations involved, can be seen in Figure 15.

Figure 15.: Roles and languages in the modeling hierarchy of ADOxx; reprinted from *On the Conceptualisation of modeling Methods Using the ADOxx Meta modeling Platform* by H.-G. Fill & D. Karagiannis, 2013, *Enterprise modeling and Information Systems Architectures*, 8(1),p.6.

6.2. Libraries

The libraries used in this prototype are implemented in the hierarchy of ADOxx (see Figure 15) on the level of the user-specific meta model as ADOxx Library Language (ALL). A library contains the definitions listed in Table 17

Content	Definition
Model Types	The base of models and contain classes and relation classes of a metamodel.
Classes	Classes serve as templates for the creation of objects, or instances, of a class.
Attributes	An attribute can be used to describe the properties of a modeling construct, such as a model, object, or relationship. Each attribute has a type and a value.
Relations	Relations classes serve as templates to create relations between objects. A relationship class is defined between classes and defines a direct connection between objects. A relationship must always have a start object and an end object.

Table 17.: Contents of the ADOxx libraries [32]

6.2.1. Bee-Up

Bee-Up is a modeling tool on the ADOxx platform, which provides the following five modeling languages [35]:

- BPMN - Business Process Model and Notation
- EPC - Event-driven Process Chains
- ER - Entity Relationship Diagrams
- UML - Unified Modeling Language
- Petri Net

Because several modeling languages are already available in Bee-Up, the tool can be used in a versatile way. In particular, it supports business process management and the modeling of IT system architectures. Because of the simple and understandable structure of the tool and the platform, Bee-Up is well suited for use in courses, schools, and universities. In addition, it is provided free of charge by the authors and the organization OMiLAB, including a detailed documentation with a case study. Figure 16 shows an excerpt from the Bee-Up Modeling Toolkit, where the available model types (diagrams) can be seen.

Figure 16.: ADOxx models of the Bee-Up tool [35]

6.2.2. TEAM

The TOGAF-based Enterprise Architecture Management (TEAM) modeling method and tool was developed by the Universities of Pretoria and Vienna. The TEAM tool provides full support of ArchiMate 3.0.1. There are dedicated model types for all ArchiMate layers. In addition, the library includes an analysis model that covers the entire ArchiMate language [6]. The toolkit and thus the library of the TEAM tool are freely available through the OMiLAB website [39]. Figure 17 shows ADOxx models of the TEAM tool.

Figure 17.: ADOxx models of the TEAM tool [39]

For the prototype of a holistic enterprise architecture toolkit, the library from the TEAM tool is merged with other libraries. This is done by creating the classes, including their attributes and graphical representations, as well as the connections in the ADOxx Development Toolkit. In addition, the various model types are recorded. In the context of this master thesis, only the elements, connectors, and model types of the ArchiMate Core Framework - i.e., the business, application, and technology layers - are initially recorded in the prototype.

6.2.3. MABBM

For modeling the e3-Value method, the MABBM library developed by Perrelet is used. In addition to the standard e3-Value modeling language, this library contains additional elements for modeling blockchain-inspired business models [28].

6.3. Implementation of Holistic Approach

The first step in prototyping the holistic approach is to create a new library called "Holistic EA" in the ADOxx platform. Because the Bee-Up library already contains most of the elements, connectors, and model types as well as coded additional functions, it was used as the basis for this new library. In a second step, all relevant elements from the TEAM and MABBM libraries were manually added to the newly created "Holistic EA" library. When all elements and connectors from the different libraries have been combined, the extension of the connection between the different modeling languages is implemented. Finally, the model types are adopted, extended, and thus adapted to the new approach of holistic enterprise architecture. The metamodel of the library can be seen in Appendix B. A detailed illustration of the class hierarchy has been omitted. This can be viewed with the ADOxx Development Toolkit by importing and opening the library.

6.3.1. Merging of the Libraries

The Bee-Up library was copied and renamed to "Holistic EA". Under the superclass "D-construct," the class "ArchiMate" was created for the elements from the TEAM library. All the classes and their attributes were then manually transferred to the newly created library. As explained in Chapter 4.2.1, the ArchiMate elements from the strategy layer, the implementation and migration layer, and the motivation aspects were excluded in the context of this thesis. All elements of the business, application and technology levels - i.e. the core framework of ArchiMate - were adopted. The distinction between the layers is also clearly visible in the library through graphical representation. In addition, during the migration of the library, the prefix "AM:" was added to the elements because there are elements and connectors with the same name in several modeling languages and therefore libraries.

Figure 18.: ArchiMate elements in Holistic EA library

The connections were recorded just below the Relation Classes folder (see Figure 19). No prefix was entered for the connectors, but "AM" was added in parentheses at the end of the connector name. The reason for this is that this system was already used in the Bee-Up library for the UML and BPMN 2.0 connectors. As the ArchiMate elements were

recorded under the ArchiMate class, this could be entered in the target and source of the connectors. This prevents connections being made between ArchiMate elements and those from other modeling languages that are not provided by the methodology.

Figure 19.: ArchiMate relations in Holistic EA library

A similar procedure was followed for the elements of the e3-Value modeling language. Here, too, an additional class called "e3-value" was created in D-construct. About half of the elements from the MABBM library were integrated into this class (see Figure 20). The other elements were recorded under the class "D-container" and the subclass "D-aggregation." In this way, the class hierarchy of the original MABBM library was retained as far as possible.

Figure 20.: MABBM elements in Holistic EA library

Only the two method-specific connectors from the MABBM library have been integrated (see Figure 21). The connector "Value Exchange" is allowed only between e3-Value specific elements, and the other connector "Connect Element" is possible for all elements and "D-Construct." This is taken from the metamodel of the modeling language, which can be seen in Perrelet's master thesis in Chapter 4.3.4 [28]. This should be reconsidered in further development of the prototype and possibly restricted further.

Figure 21.: MABBM relations in Holistic EA library

6.3.2. Model Types

The three merged libraries already implemented their own model types and associated filters. Because of the increased complexity and scope of the merger, the groupings and filters have been redesigned. There are now the following groupings of model types that can be filtered in the modeling toolkit. In addition, a new group with three model types has been created so that the links between the detailed architectures and the enterprise architecture can be represented in ArchiMate. Table 18 shows the model types for the holistic EA prototype.

Grouping	Model Types	Description
All model types	<i>All</i>	This group contains all available model types.
ArchiMate	Application Layer Business Layer Technology Layer Analysis Model	This group contains the ArchiMate views and elements. The model types come from the TEAM library.
e3-Value	e3-Value	This group contains only one model type, for e3- Value. The basis for this was the MABBM library.
BPMN 2.0	Business Process Diagram Company Map Decision Requirements Diagram Document Model Flowchart Working Environment Model	This group contains the model types around BPMN. The model types were adopted from the Bee-Up library.
UML	Activity Diagram Class / Object Diagram Classifier Pool Communication Diagram Component Diagram Composite Structure Diagram Deployment Diagram Interaction Overview Diagram Package Diagram Sequence Diagram State Machine Diagram Timing Diagram Use Case Diagram	This group contains the model types of UML. The model types were adopted from the Bee-Up Library.
Others	ER Model Petri Nets EPC Model	This group contains further model types that have been adopted from the Bee-Up library.
Holistic EA	Holistic EA - Business Layer Holistic EA - Application Layer Holistic EA - Technology Layer	This group contains the model types that are used to create the relationship between the detailed architectures and the enterprise architecture.
Custom	<i>Customised</i>	This group allows the user to create a personalized filter from all available model types.

Table 18.: Model types Holistic EA prototype

6.3.3. Extensions Holistic EA

Besides the extension of the new model types - Holistic EA - a new connector and the possibility for links between the modeling languages were added. These enable the holistic enterprise architecture approach described in the Chapter 5 to be mapped in the ADOxx tool.

New Connector

To enable the connection between the modeling in e3-Value, BPMN 2.0, UML to the modeling in ArchiMate, the connector "RepresentedBy" was added. This connector provides information about which ArchiMate elements another architectural element represents in the overall architecture.

Connector	Representation	Attribute
RepresentedBy <i>Specifies which ArchiMate element (target) represents the element (source) in the enterprise architecture.</i>		Description <i>This attribute gives the user the possibility to enter additional annotations for the connection.</i>

Table 19.: Details of the relation "RepresentedBy"

To create a connector, the appropriate Holistic EA model type is selected and the elements to be connected are mapped to it. It is important that the connector points to an ArchiMate element. This means that the starting point is an e3-Value, BPMN 2.0 or UML element and the end point of the connector is the ArchiMate element. For the purpose of clarity, it is recommended to create several Holistic EA diagrams. The subdivision can vary depending on the context of the business or use case.

New Attributes

For the approach proposed in this thesis regarding the loose coupling of architectural content in different modeling languages, new attributes of type Inter-model reference (INTERREF) have been added in ADOxx to the Holistic EA library. The attribute enables a reference to an existing diagram (Model reference) or directly to an existing element (Instance reference). The reference type must therefore be defined in the library and then which model types and classes can be referenced. In this prototype, the attributes have been created according to the table 20.

Attribute	Reference type	Description
Link to Diagram	Model references	Reference to all model types of the groups e3-Value, BPMN 2.0, UML and others in accordance with Table 18.
Link to e3-Value Elements	Instance references	Reference to all e3-value elements in accordance with Figure 20.
Link to BPMN 2.0 Elements	Instance references	Reference to all BPMN 2.0 elements available in the Business Process Diagram model type.
Link to UML Elements	Instance references	Reference to all UML elements available in the UML model types in accordance with Table 18.

Table 20.: New Interref-Attributes

Due to the character limit of the interref attribute in ADOxx, not all possible ULM elements could be stored in the Link to UML elements attribute. For this reason the elements have been swapped out and stored in the "Interref-UML.leo" file. The command in the file is structured in the same way as in the Interref attribute. For example, for two elements it is as follows:

```
REFDOMAIN
OBJREF
    mt: "Activity Diagram
    c: "Action (UML)".
OBJREF
    mt: "Activity Diagram
    c: "Activity (UML)".
```

The file has been loaded into the Holistic EA library via the ADOxx file manager and can be extended as required. In the Interref attribute, the following command has been stored in the field AttributeInterRefDomain:

```
@INCLUDE("db:\Interref-UML.leo")
```

A restriction on the number of possible links by cardinality has not been used here in order to give the user maximum flexibility. However, this could be examined in a further development of the approach and adapted if necessary. This and other possibilities for improving the approach are described in the Chapter 8.

The user of the prototype can store the links in the notebook of the elements. For this purpose, the tab "Links" has been inserted at the end of the notebook for each element. The figure 22 shows the notebook with the possible Interref-Attributes.

Figure 22.: Example of links in a notebook

7

Evaluation

According to the DSR method described in Chapter 2, one component of the process is evaluation, which was iterative. Findings from the evaluation have been analyzed and fed back into the design. This chapter describes the results of the evaluation of the two artifacts developed: the holistic approach and the prototype. A scenario-based evaluation was performed with the developed prototype and the described methodology for a holistic enterprise architecture to test the suitability of the approach in practice. For this purpose, a fictitious company was used to capture several architectural views. The goal was to show how the individual architectural views can be mapped using the various modeling languages in ADOxx and linked to form an overall model.

In a second step, it is evaluated whether the advantages of a holistic Enterprise Architecture — as discussed in research question one — can be exploited with the approach and the prototype. In addition, the strengths, weaknesses, opportunities, and threats are identified and described using the common SWOT analysis. This evaluation is intended to identify and indicate future further developments.

7.1. Scenario-based Evaluation

The prototype and the proposed approach were tested for usability. For this purpose, an example use case is employed to present the content in a meaningful way. The example is based on the case used by the Swiss Army for training in enterprise architecture and the methods developed in-house [22].

The goal of the scenario-based evaluation is to determine whether architectural content can be represented with the method and whether the connection between the architectural levels and languages can be represented in a meaningful way. In a further step, the scenario-based evaluation should show whether the libraries have been combined correctly and whether the extension has been implemented correctly. Findings from the scenario-based evaluation flow back into the design phase (if adjustments are needed) and into the final evaluation. The scenario-based evaluation was constantly extended and was performed several times during the thesis. Following are excerpts from the scenario-based evaluation.

7.1.1. Introduction to the Example

The company Train Ltd wishes to document its enterprise architecture in a model-based way to make strategic decisions in the future. The architectures are to be captured centrally in a tool by various specialists in the company. The enterprise architect should have an overall view of the architecture and map the most important components with the ArchiMate modeling language. Ultimately, the enterprise architect is also the link to the strategy and is in upper management. The remainder of the architecture creation is based on TOGAF's ADM Cycle. The business architect is responsible for representing the business models using the e3-Value method as well as the process landscape, which they map using the BPMN 2.0 language. The process manager supports the business architect in collecting and documenting the processes. The IT architects in the company are more concerned with the technical architectures, such as the information system architecture and the technology architecture. Their main products are system maps and solution architectures. These are described in the UML modeling language.

Using the process "Ticket sales" and the required application "Ticket system", it is shown how the modeling could look like in the different architectures and how a holistic view is made possible. Figure 23 shows which models are created at which architectural levels to represent the process and the system. The example of the business process shows how the linking to other architectures works.

Figure 23.: Overview of the model types and linkages of the example

7.1.2. Folder Structure

Train Ltd's enterprise architect has decided that the different architects should have their own section in the enterprise modeling tool. He has followed the structure according to TOGAF and ArchiMate. For himself, he has the Enterprise Architecture folder, where the rough overall architecture is recorded in the ArchiMate modeling language, and the Holistic EA folder, where he maintains the link between the individual architecture models together with the other architects in the company. The business architect has focused on business processes and value models in his architecture area. He uses BPMN 2.0 for the modeling of processes and the e3-Value method for the value models. In Train Ltd there are Application, Infrastructure and Solution Architects. The application architect models his UML diagrams in the Information Systems Architecture section. The Infrastructure Architect has the Technology Architecture folder. The solution architect has a special role, as he basically only works in projects. He works very closely with all architects and, depending on the context, needs architecture content from all areas. Figure 24 shows the folder structure in ADOxx of Train Ltd's architecture modeling.

Figure 24.: Example: Folder structure Explorer ADOxx

7.1.3. Enterprise Architecture

For the enterprise architect, it is first and foremost important to have an overview of the architecture of the enterprise so that it can be aligned with the strategic guidelines and investments can be planned. For this reason, the enterprise architect, together with the business architect, has created a process landscape with the most important business processes or their groupings and, with the technical specialists, an application landscape with the strategically important IT systems. Figures 25 and 26 show the two maps of the enterprise architect, modelled with ArchiMate.

Process Landscape 1.0 (Business Layer)

Object count: 17

Figure 25.: Example: Enterprise Architecture - Process Landscape

Application Landscape (Application Layer)

Object count: 17

Figure 26.: Example: Enterprise Architecture - Application Landscape

On the ArchiMate analysis models, the enterprise architect combines elements from the three layers to represent a specific context. Figure 27 shows an extract from the Business Unit Sales where the Enterprise Architect has modelled the context of the Ticket system. This modeling is used as the system context for the as-is analysis in the project "Replacement of the old Ticket system".

BU Sales (Analysis Model)

Object count: 22

Figure 27.: Example: Enterprise Architecture - Analysis Model BU Sales

7.1.4. Business Architecture

The business architect of Train Ltd needs a more detailed overview of the enterprise processes than the enterprise architect. Process groupings such as "public transport" are not enough for them to manage and develop their architecture. For this reason, he has created a separate overview for himself for the management processes, core processes and support processes. Then, for each process, there is a BPMN diagram that shows the business process in detail. Figure 28 shows the overview of the core processes. Figure 29 then shows the diagram of the business process (BP) ticket sales counter.

Figure 28.: Example: Business Architecture - Overview Core Processes

The processes in the overview are each linked to the corresponding diagram with the modelled detailed process. For this purpose, the business architect has stored the diagram for the business process in the notebook under Links in the attribute "Link to diagram". This allows him to jump directly from the overview to the diagram. Figure 29 shows the "Ticket sales counter" process modelled with BPMN 2.0.

Figure 29.: Example: Business Architecture - Process "Ticket sales counter"

It is recommended to use the ADOxx function of the references. There the user can see directly which links exist from the elements to this diagram. Figure 30 at the bottom left the reference from the "Ticket sales counter" element on the Overview Core Processes diagram to the diagram "BP: Ticket sales counter".

Figure 30.: Example: Business Architecture - References

In addition to business processes, it is also important for the business architect to model business models. This enables him to map which value is exchanged with which actors via which interfaces. Figure 31 shows a very simplified model in the e3-Value Method modeling language. The model shows that the customer announces his need for transport to Train Ltd. This service is paid for by the customer and therefore the value exchange here is transport for money.

Figure 31.: Example: Business Architecture - e3-Value Method

For the "Customer" element, the business architect has stored in the notebook a link to the lane "Customer" from the previously described process in the notebook. This allows him to make statements about which process achieves the value flow according to the e3-Value Model.

7.1.5. Information System Architecture

In the Information System Architecture folder, a separate area has been created for each Business Unit (BU). This is where the applications and data for each BU are managed and architecturally represented. In this example, the ticketing system is located in the Sales business unit. In the relevant folder, the application architect has now created a class diagram for the Ticket system and ticket sales at the counter. The class diagram is shown in figure 32.

Figure 32.: Example: Information System Architecture - Class Diagram Ticket sales counter

To show the similarities between these two models and architectural levels, the architect has placed various links to the business process in the UML elements notebook, as shown in Figure 33. Another benefit of such a link is the identification of possible misunderstandings or differences in naming. In this example, it is clear that the business architect refers to "customers" and the IT architects refer to "clients".

Another link that the IT architect has created here is the link to the deployment diagram from the technology architecture. This allows him to make the jump to the technical components and the structure of his Ticket system.

Figure 33.: Example: Information System Architecture - Links to BPMN 2.0 elements

7.1.6. Technology Architecture

Train Ltd's IT architect is responsible for the company's technical architecture. For the Ticket system, not only hardware such as clients, but also databases and interfaces are required. These are shown in the deployment diagram in Figure 34

Figure 34.: Example: Technology Architecture - Deployment Diagram Database for Ticket system

7.1.7. Holistic EA

To establish the link between the enterprise architecture and the more detailed architectures, the enterprise architect uses the model types of the Holistic EA. The following three figures show extracts from these model types.

Figure ?? shows the link between the enterprise architect's process overview and that of the business architect. The different levels of granularity are well illustrated. For example, if the business architect wants to develop the ticket counter process and needs to make a strategic decision, he knows from this model that he needs to refer to the main public transport process. The enterprise architect can then analyse the change in the enterprise architecture accordingly, as shown in Figure 27.

Figure 35.: Example: Holistic EA - Connected processes

However, in his analysis, the enterprise architect also needs more information about the technical implementation of the ticketing system. Again, he has links to the other architectures in his holistic EA models, as shown in Figures 36 and 37. He can now go directly to the corresponding models to gather information, or he can go to the responsible IT architect and clarify open questions there.

Figure 36.: Example: Holistic EA - Connected applications

Figure 37.: Example: Holistic EA - Connected components

7.1.8. Conclusion of the Scenario-based Evaluation

The evaluation based on the example of Train Ltd. shows well the advantages of the methodology and the prototype, but also the limitations and disadvantages. With the Holistic EA library and ADOxx, several architects of a company can work together and create a holistic architecture. Decentralised knowledge is thus documented in a central place, enabling faster evaluation and decision-making. In particular, by storing the reference between the enterprise architecture and the detailed architectures, as well as the links between the architectures, statements can be prepared more easily and efficiently. Although the links have no or only weak semantics, it is better to have a link than none. At least you know that there is some kind of dependency and that you need to include something. This is particularly evident in the Business Unit Sales analysis model. This is the relevant system context for the project and serves as the starting point for further specifications, be they the processes or some technical architecture.

A disadvantage of this approach is that certain elements have to be captured more than once. For example, the processes from the enterprise architecture process landscape and the business architecture process overview have to be captured again in the holistic EA models. In other modeling tools, a database is often linked so that elements can only be captured once and then reused.

In summary, the various standard modeling languages and the prototype of the library can be used to create a holistic architecture in a very simple way.

7.2. Assessment of the Modeling Methodology and Prototype

The benefits to an organization of the holistic enterprise architecture approach and prototype described here can be estimated from Figure 3. The approach can add value to both business and IT in the short term by providing transparency about the relevant elements and along with documented information. The approach also considers the different roles and needs. The roles involved in architecture have different levels of expertise and are often accustomed to tools and modeling languages through experience and education. This is addressed here by providing a simple tool and a holistic approach. By providing the strategy level with a holistic view of the enterprise architecture in the medium term, decisions can be made in a business-oriented and resource-oriented manner. This is also achieved by linking business and IT. Alignment with the ArchiMate models can be achieved together with the coupling between the individual architecture models at the operational level.

It is not only companies that can benefit from this holistic approach. Architecture and modeling are important topics - especially in the education of specialists in computer science and business informatics. This approach and prototype can be used in education to teach the subject holistically. The scenario from chapter 7.1 can also be used, as this demonstrates the approach well by means of an example.

7.2.1. SWOT Analysis

A SWOT analysis was carried out in order to evaluate the methodological approach and the prototype in a more precise and differentiated way. For this purpose, the results of the scenario-based evaluation and the general evaluation were used. From this, possible improvements and further developments can be derived. The table 21 shows the details of the SWOT analysis.

	Strengths	Weaknesses
Methodology	SM1: Holistic approach	WM1: Increased modeling effort
	SM2: Different roles and demands addressed	WM2: Loose linking
Prototype	SP1: Open source	WP1: Multi-entry
	SP2: Quick to use	WP2: Incomplete ArchiMate
	Opportunities	Threats
Methodology	OM1: Can be enhanced	TM1: Missing Commitment
	OM2: Tool independent applicable	TM2: New approaches
Prototype	OP1: Can be enhanced	TP1: Different tools
	OP2: Further example of use	TP2: Support ADOxx

Table 21.: SWOT analysis

SWOT Internal Analysis

The internal view in a SWOT analysis is about self-observation and factors that can be influenced by the company itself. In the context of this thesis, therefore, strengths were identified, and weaknesses could have been addressed. However, some of these were consciously excepted (see Table 22).

ID	Description
SM1:	This approach already covers a large part of the TOGAF ADM cycle. It enables a representation of an overall architecture in the ArchiMate language as well as more detailed architectures using additional modeling languages. These are interconnected by this approach and can be brought into the overall context.
SM2:	As described in Chapter 3.3, several roles are involved in the discipline of architecture. Accordingly, different frameworks and methods have been established in practice that are oriented toward the tasks of these roles. This holistic approach considers this by linking the different languages. In this way, the experts can continue to use their usual language and an overall picture or architecture can still be created.
SP1:	The ADOxx platform is open source and therefore freely accessible. This makes it possible to use the presented approach and the developed prototype.
SP2:	Because of the strength of an open source product, the prototype is also quickly applicable; i.e., it can be installed quickly and easily. In addition, compared to other EAM tools, ADOxx has a simple structure and is easy to understand.
WM1:	The fact that multiple modeling languages are allowed means that the same models can be modeled multiple times. This creates extra work for architects who wish to have an architecture or a statement represented in their language. This requires leadership support.
WM2:	The proposed approach includes only a loose connection and textual description possibility between the modeling languages e3-Value, BPMN 2.0, and UML. This means that the semantics of the connection must be stored and interpreted when using prose descriptions, which makes a common understanding and the standardization of modeling more difficult.
WP1:	If ADOxx is used without an underlying database, the same elements must be entered multiple times. This means that if, for example, the same element is used on several diagrams, it must be entered repeatedly.
WP2:	The method does not describe the entire ArchiMate framework because the Strategy and Implementation and Migration layers have been excluded for this thesis. If these were to be included in a use case, the prototype would have to be supplemented.

Table 22.: Description of internal SWOT analysis

SWOT External Analysis

The external view of a SWOT analysis refers to the assessment of opportunities and threats that arise from external circumstances and over which there is only limited or no influence possible. In this thesis, these are factors that could not be influenced and will be considered in a later application of the approach or prototype. It is necessary to adapt the strategy to use the opportunities and eliminate or at least minimize the dangers. See Table 23.

ID	Description
OM1:	The method has great potential for further development. Missing ArchiMate layers or additional modeling languages can be included, and the references and links can be extended if necessary.
OM2:	Theoretically, the approach presented here for a holistic enterprise architecture can also be applied using another tool that includes the modeling languages and can be supplemented with extensions.
OP1:	The prototype can be further developed using more modeling languages, better semantics, or implemented workflows. Because of the concept of ADOxx, extending the library is simple and can be done quickly.
OP2:	When the prototype is used in practice, such as a course, further and more detailed use cases can be developed, documented, and made available. This can increase the benefit and the number of users of the prototype.
TM1:	There may be a lack of commitment to a holistic enterprise architecture at the strategic level. This is the result of insufficient resources (staff, time, budget) or a lack of acceptance and support in the company.
TM2:	New approaches are constantly being developed and presented from both research and practice. An alternative approach to holistic enterprise architecture may emerge.
TP1:	Many specialists have already become accustomed to existing tools and may not want to change to another. This creates the risk that so-called “shadow architectures” are captured in other tools.
TP2:	Because the prototype runs on the ADOxx platform, it is dependent on the nonprofit organization OMiLAB. This organization provides the platform and offers best-effort support. In case of problems, there is no guaranteed fast support.

Table 23.: Description of external SWOT analysis

8

Discussion and Outlook

Following on from the SWOT analysis in the previous chapter, this chapter describes possible further development measures. These measures should take advantage of identified opportunities and eliminate or minimize weaknesses. Whether and how these measures are taken is not part of this thesis but serves as a possible starting point for research.

8.1. Additional Connections to the Enterprise Architecture

As described in Chapter 5.1, the approach presented in this thesis mainly considers the connections to the ArchiMate model, which are described in existing concepts such as Lankhorst's or are easy to understand even for those with little knowledge of architectural models. With a deeper analysis or even a trial application in a larger context, additional connections could be elicited - especially with the modeling language UML, there would likely be additional possibilities to connect to the application and technology layers of ArchiMate. To make this extension, simply adapt the metamodel and ensure in the library that the connector "RepresentedBy" (see Chapter 6.3.2) can be modeled between the corresponding elements. This is a possible measure to use the opportunities OM1 and OP1.

8.2. ArchiMate Full Framework

One identified weakness is WP2: Incomplete ArchiMate, which states that the complete ArchiMate full framework has not been implemented. One measure would therefore be to implement the remaining elements of the Strategic, Motivation, and Implementation/Migration layers from the TEAM library in the same way as the other layers.

This would also allow OM1 to be used to enhance the method. More links between more elements are possible. Example: Requirements from the ArchiMate motivation aspect can be linked to UML elements. In this way it is possible to express which use cases or IT components the requirements refer to.

8.3. Extension of Loose Coupling of Elements

Another identified weakness is the approach to loose linking between elements of the modeling languages e3-Value, BPMN 2.0 and UML (WM2: Loose linking). To address this, semantic meaning could be added to the links in a next development step. Possible specifications of connections could include the following:

- Depends on
- Is a specialization of
- Uses
- Gets Management; Gets Support
- Relates to
- Is equal to
- Refine

If the approach were to be extended to include these links, or at least parts of them, it would need to be methodologically well elaborated. Doing so would also require a formal definition of what the link means and how it is to be used. There is also the possibility of defining further restrictions, i.e., to define which elements may be connected. For example, the connector “gets management” may point only to a UML component because the statement is that another system is managed by this component. These extensions would then need to be added in the prototype. Here it must be considered whether work with interrefs in attributes should continue or whether these are additional connectors that can be modeled in a special view (model type).

8.4. Extension with Additional Modeling Languages

In addition to extending the full ArchiMate methodology, other modeling languages can be included in the approach and in the prototype. This would address the OM1 and OP1 opportunities regarding enhancement. To add further modeling languages, the methodology needs to analyze the layers on which the modeling language moves and which ArchiMate elements can represent certain information in the enterprise architecture. Furthermore, the new elements and connectors must be recorded in the Holistic EA library, including the relevant attributes. However, it is worth first confirming whether a library with these elements is already available in the OMiLAB community. In this case, it can be merged rather than reentered. The model types also need to be adapted so that the new modeling languages can be used in the modeling toolkit.

One possibility would be to add the business model canvas (BMC) method. This is similar to the e3-Value method and is also located on the Business layer. This would offer added value especially if the Motivation and Strategic layer of ArchiMate is also implemented. In 2012, Meertens et al. published an approach for mapping between BMC and ArchiMate. According to the authors, the creation and analysis of possible business

models should serve as a starting point for the design process. This should then be translated into an enterprise architecture and further refined. For the business models, they recommend Osterwalder's BMC methodology. This considers and describes the following nine elements: key partners, key activities, key resources, value propositions, customer relationships, customer segments, channels, cost structure, and revenue streams [24].

As an alternative or supplement to BPMN 2.0 modeling, the event-driven process chain (EPC) method could be used. The EPC modeling language was originally developed as a reference process model for SAP software and modeled using the ARIS tool. EPC includes activities, gateways, and events but does not allow any additional characterization compared to BPMN 2.0. The reading direction also differs from BPMN 2.0: EPC is modeled from top to bottom and is similar to a flowchart. Although EPC is easier to read and understand than BPMN 2.0 because of the smaller number of symbol types, ARIS and SAP have also switched to the OMG standard [10]. Nevertheless, it may be that EPC is still used in companies precisely because of its simplicity, so that an extension of the method for the holistic approach would be a possibility. The advantage here is that the elements and a model type are already present in the prototype because this was taken from the Bee-Up library.

8.5. Further Development

In addition to the extensions proposed in the previous chapters, others may be considered. However, these require more effort for analysis and development. In this thesis, only a rough indication of what could be investigated in more detail is provided.

8.5.1. Automatically Store Bidirectional Function

With ADOscript, the ADOxx platform provides a procedural scripting language that allows ADOxx functions to be controlled by programs. This could be used to store a script that automatically generates interrefs based on other interrefs. This could be used to automate the linking described in Chapter 5.2. For example, if a UML element is linked to a BPMN 2.0 element by an interref, the BPMN 2.0 element will automatically create an interref link to the UML. In this way, bidirectional links can be created with little additional effort. The ADOxx community has already developed a possible implementation, which can be read about in the FAQ forum [33].

8.5.2. Annotation Concept

In addition to the previously described measure for the weakness of loose coupling with extensions of additional reference types or connectors, another possibility would be to couple the approach with the concept of semantic annotation described by Fill, 2018. This would provide a way to store additional ontologies without having to adapt the underlying metamodel [12]. The advantage is that this approach is available on the ADOxx platform with the Semantic-based Modeling Framework for Information Systems (SeMFIS) tool.

8.6. Further Uses

As described in the SWOT analysis, one strength is the easy and quick availability (SP1 and SP2). This makes it easy to use ADOxx and the Holistic EA library in the classroom, which means that students can be introduced to several modeling languages as well as the different layers according to TOGAF and ArchiMate. The identified opportunity "OP2: Further example of use" would thus also be covered. If the approach and the prototype are used in the classroom, new use cases will emerge that could in turn help others. The existing approach and the contents of this thesis also provide a basis for a study project. Some possible developments are described; others could be analyzed and implemented. To achieve this, the approach and the prototype (the Holistic EA library) will be made publicly available.

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A

Deployment of the Prototype - Library Holistic EA

This master thesis is freely available via the Zenodo platform. Furthermore, the prototype (the developed library) and the modeled scenario, according to Chapter 7.1, are also published.

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The publication includes the following materials:

1. Masterthesis: "MT_Alexandra_Fankhauser.pdf"
2. ADOxx Library: "Library Holistic EA.abl"
3. Modeled scenario: "Scenario-based Evaluation Holistic EA.adl"

B

Meta Model Library Holistic EA

Figure 38.: Meta model of the Holistic EA Library

ERKLÄRUNG

Ich bestätige mit meiner Unterschrift, dass ich die Arbeit persönlich erstellt und dabei nur die aufgeführten Quellen und Hilfsmittel verwendet sowie wörtliche Zitate und Paraphrasen als solche gekennzeichnet habe.

Es ist mir bekannt, dass andernfalls die Fakultät gemäss der Entscheidung des Fakultätsrats vom 09.11.2004 das Recht hat, den auf Grund dieser Arbeit verliehenen Titel zu entziehen.

Ich erkläre hiermit weiterhin, dass diese Arbeit bzw. Teile daraus noch nicht in dieser Form an anderer Stelle als Prüfungsleistung eingereicht worden sind, gemäss der Entscheidung des Fakultätsrats vom 18.11.2013.

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